

LONG-TERM OPEN HOLE COMPRESSION STRENGTH OF CFRP LAMINATES BASED ON STRAIN INVARIANT FAILURE THEORY

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SUMMARY: This paper deals with the prediction of long term strength of CFRP structure components based on the combined method of the strain invariant failure theory (SIFT) and the accelerated testing methodology (ATM) developed by Tsai and others. The time-temperature dependent master curves of SIFT critical parameters were constructed by tension and compression tests for the longitudinal and transverse directions of unidirectional CFRP under various temperatures based on the time-temperature superposition principle which holds for the viscoelastic modulus of matrix resin. The long term open hole compression strength of the quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates was predicted using the master curves of SIFT critical parameters based on SIFT/ATM combined method and structural stress and strain analysis by finite element method. The applicability of SIFT/ATM combined method to predict the long term strength of CFRP structures was experimentally confirmed.

KEY WORDS: open hole compression, strength, strain invariant failure theory, accelerated testing methodology, time-temperature dependence

INTRODUCTION

Since a resin matrix exhibits characteristic time and temperature dependence on mechanical behaviour, that is, viscoelasticity behaviour, CFRP laminates is expected to exhibit similar behaviour [1-3]. In our previous papers [4-6], the constant strain-rate (CSR), creep and fatigue strengths of CFRP laminates were studied under various loading rates and temperatures. The accelerated testing methodology (ATM) was proposed for the prediction of long-term fatigue strength of CFRP laminates based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP) and the applicability of this methodology was confirmed for all of CFRP structures combined with PAN based carbon fibres and thermosetting resins. The master curves generated by ATM are unique for each material and failure modes, and can serve as a material durability database, being capable of predicting the strength and life under a wide ranges of loading conditions, temperature and time to failure.

Gosse and Christensen [7] proposed a new failure criterion for CFRP that can predict initial and final failures of composite laminates and structure based on the strain invariant failure theory (SIFT) in which the failure is governed by three critical parameters, that is the equivalent strains of carbon fibre and the equivalent and volumetric strains of matrix resin.

Tsai and his colleagues [8] developed the Super Mic-Mac software to predict the long term strength of CFRP laminates based on SIFT/ATM combined method, which was limited to the in-plane analysis of multi-directional CFRP laminates. Essentially, the SIFT/ATM combined method can relate the basic material durability properties to those laminates with complex stacking sequences and geometries, thus enhancing the applicability of the database and also reducing the number of tests required to generate the database.

In our previous paper [9], the applicability of SIFT/ATM combined method was experimentally confirmed by predicting the long term compressive strength of quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates (QIL) at various temperatures and loading rates. The present paper will extend the applicability of the SIFT/ATM combined method, focusing on the prediction of the long term strength of composite structure components. The time-temperature dependent master curves of SIFT critical parameters were constructed according to tension and compression tests for the longitudinal and transverse directions of unidirectional CFRP (UD) under various temperatures and measuring the time-temperature shift factor of storage modulus of matrix resin. The long term open hole compression (OHC) strength of QIL was predicted using the master curves of SIFT critical parameters based on SIFT/ATM combined method and structural stress and strain analysis by finite element method. The predicted values are compared with the actual experimental data.

THEORETICAL BASIS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Strain Invariant failure theory

Because the matrix is isotropic, its yield under complex stress must directly result from the intensity of stress or strain, and be independent of the direction of the coordinate system. Failure will be governed by either volumetric expansion or strain bias-induced flow of the polymer.

$$\text{Volumetric Strain} = J_1 + J_2 + J_3 \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} J_1 &= \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 + \epsilon_3 \\ J_2 &= \epsilon_1\epsilon_2 + \epsilon_1\epsilon_3 + \epsilon_2\epsilon_3 \\ J_3 &= \epsilon_1\epsilon_2\epsilon_3 \end{aligned}$$

Where, ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , and ϵ_3 are the three principal strains, J_i are the invariants of the strain tensor.

The reduced form of the volumetric strain is

$$J_1 = \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 + \epsilon_3 . \quad (2)$$

For the second strain invariant, the von Mises equivalent strain is used. The von Mises equivalent strain is the function of the invariants J_1 and J_2 .

$$\epsilon_{eqv} = \{0.5[(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)^2 + (\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_3)^2 + (\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_3)^2]\}^{0.5} = (J_1^2 - 3J_2)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

Both the volumetric strain (the first invariant of the strain) and the equivalent strain (a function of the second invariant of the strain deviator tensor) are strain invariants.

Hart-Smith and Gosse [10] indicated that Grosse's strain-invariant formulation of failure criteria for the resin matrix in fiber-polymer composites is adaptable to predict the strength of CFRP laminate by fiber failure as well. Since the carbon fiber is orthotropic (transversely isotropic), and the failure being triggered by shape change, therefore, only the equivalent strain is used as failure criterion. Because the tensile strength and compressive strength are very different for strength of carbon fibre, two critical equivalent strains are necessary for tensile and compressive fiber failures, respectively.

In Grosse's model, the micromechanical effect and thermal residual strains from curing temperature are considered. In this research, the FEM model of hexagonal unit-cell for magnification factor is used, showed in Fig.1. The micro-level strains are recalculated in 17 points in fiber and 19 points in matrix by magnification factors got from the prior FEM analysis.

The failure is decided by the failure index FI, expressed as following,

$$FI = \text{Maximum} (\epsilon_{eqv}^f / \epsilon_{eqv}^{f,cr}, \epsilon_{eqv}^m / \epsilon_{eqv}^{m,cr}, J_1^m / J_1^{cr}) \quad (4)$$

where, the superscript cr implies the critical value.

Once the failure index value in the specimen or structure exceeds unity, the interior crack will initiate locally.

Fig. 1: FEM model of hexagonal unit-cell for strain magnification factors

SIFT/ATM procedure

The SIFT/ATM method for construction of master curve of CFRP laminate consists of five steps. Measure the ultimate strains of UD laminate by tensile or compressive tests. Modify the macro-strain of the homogenized lamina by magnification factor from finite element solution for unit-cell. Calculate the SIFT critical parameters in micro-level for fiber and matrix. Get shift factor for matrix resin by dynamic viscoelastic tests. Apply this shift factor to SIFT critical parameters to construct the master curves.

The effective properties of fiber, matrix and lamina are necessary to calculate the magnification factor, and subsequent application of the SIFT critical parameter master curves. The effective properties of fiber, matrix and lamina used in the research include the Young's moduli, the shear moduli, the Poisson's ratios and coefficients of thermal expansion. The time-temperature dependent effect on resin and laminate should be considered.

After the construction of the master curves for the SIFT critical parameters has been done, the master curves of the strength of laminate bearing simple load or composite laminate structure bearing complex load can be constructed by strain analysis for each lamina of the laminate or

strain field analysis for the structure by finite element method. The master curve of strength obtained for the laminate or for composite structure can be applied to predict the long term strength or the life under assigned load. In this research, the long term OHC strength for QIL will be investigated.

EXPERIMENTS

Material

The CFRP test specimens were fabricated from UD laminate and QIL $[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$ of TR30S/epoxy. All the laminates were made by hot pressing technique. The curing procedure includes 130°C for 1hour and 150°C for 2hours, and subsequent 75°C for 7500min physical aging to increase Young's modulus. The volume fraction of fiber is approximately 0.6. The laminates were cut by diamond-grit wheel to the specific size for the tests. The specimen size and configuration are shown in Figs.2 and 3.

Test procedures

As mentioned above, there are four SIFT critical parameters for one material. Accordingly, four tests are necessary to get these critical parameters, including unidirectional tension and compression for fiber, $\epsilon_{\text{eqv}}^{\text{f,t}}$ and $\epsilon_{\text{eqv}}^{\text{f,c}}$, transverse tension and compression tests for matrix, J_1 and $\epsilon_{\text{eqv}}^{\text{m}}$. In this research, check tests has been done to get critical equivalent strain for matrix shearing failure. Comparing to 20 degree off-axis tension test, the transverse compression test demonstrates the maximum equivalent strain. Thus, the transverse compression tests were used to get critical equivalent strain for matrix shearing failure. Figure 2 shows the configurations and sizes of UD specimens. The tensile and compressive tests are conducted at five levels of temperatures RT, 50, 80, 120, 140°C , and loading rate 1 mm/min.

Fig.2: Configuration of unidirectional specimens

It is well known that the compressive strength of laminate behaves strong time-temperature dependence. The OHC tests for QIL under various strain rates and temperatures are conducted to validate the time-temperature dependence of compressive strengths obtained from SIFT critical parameters master curves. A fixture for OHC test proposed by National Aerospace Laboratory (NAL III) was used. Figure 3 shows the configurations and sizes of

QIL specimens. The test temperatures are RT, 80, 140°C, the loading rates are 10, 0.1, 0.001 mm/min.

Fig.3: Configuration of open hole QIL specimens for compression tests

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Master curve of storage modulus for matrix resin

The left side of Fig.4 shows the storage modulus E' versus time t for the epoxy which is the matrix resin of CFRP laminate, where time t is half of the inverse of frequency f , i.e. $1/(2f)$. The right side shows the master curve of E' which was constructed by shifting E' at various constant temperatures along the logarithmic scale of t until they overlapped each other, for the reduced time t' at the reference temperature $T_0=25^\circ\text{C}$. Since E' at various constant temperatures can be superimposed so that a smooth curve is constructed, the TTSP is applicable for the storage modulus of epoxy resin.

Fig.4: Master curve of storage modulus of epoxy resin

Figure 5 shows the time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ obtained experimentally for the master curve of the storage modulus of epoxy resin. The shift factors are quantitatively in good agreement with Arrhenius' equation with two activation energies ΔH_1 and ΔH_2 ;

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad (5)$$

where G is the gas constant, 8.314×10^{-3} [kJ/(K•mol)].

The time-temperature shift factor obtained from the dynamic viscoelastic test is adopted to calculate the reduced time to failure t'_s which are necessary to construct the master curves of SIFT critical parameters for the CFRP laminate.

$$t'_s = \frac{t_s}{a_{T_0}(T)} \quad (6)$$

Fig.5: Time-temperature shift factors of epoxy resin

Stress-strain curves for the UD laminate

Stress-strain curves of UD longitudinal and transverse tension and compression tests are shown in Figs.6 and 7. The stress-strain curves of longitudinal tension and compression tests are roughly linear until maximum stress, and the stresses drop suddenly at maximum stress for all specimens. The stress-strain curves of transverse tension and compression tests are roughly linear at low temperatures, and nonlinear at high temperatures. The Young's moduli at initial points were obtained for strain analysis of followed QIL compression tests.

Fig.6: Stress versus strain of tension

Fig.7: Stress versus strain of compression

Master curves of SIFT critical parameters

Based on above CSR test results of UD laminate, the construction of master curves of SIFT critical parameters become possible. The basis is that the time-temperature dependence of CFRP laminate is same with that of matrix epoxy resin. Figure 7 shows the master curves of SIFT critical parameters for TR30S/epoxy. The tensile equivalent strain of fiber decreases a little with increase of the reduced time t'_s . It means that the tensile equivalent strain of fiber is not strongly time-temperature dependent. However, the curves of compressive equivalent strain of fiber, the first strain invariant and the von Mises equivalent strain of matrix epoxy show strong time-temperature dependence. The compressive equivalent strain of fiber decreases apparently with the increase of reduced time t'_s . The first strain invariant of matrix epoxy also decreases with the increase of reduced time t'_s . This increase results from the change of Poisson's ratio of epoxy with temperature. The Poisson's ratio of epoxy changes from 0.35 at room temperature to about 0.5 at high temperature 140°C. The master curve of the von Mises equivalent strain indicates increasing with the increase of reduced time t'_s . The equivalent strain relates the shape change, rather the volume dilatation. At high temperature, or long failure time, the matrix resin becomes weak, and the shape change is easy.

Fig.7: Master curves of SIFT critical parameters for TR30S/epoxy

Open hole compressive strength prediction for the QIL

The validity of the master curves of the SIFT parameters was checked by the prediction of long term OHC strength of QIL. The failure mechanism of compressive QIL was investigated by comparing the failure index in each plies by ANSYS codes. At room temperature, the normalized failure index in Fig.8 shows that the compressive equivalent strain in fibers triggered the failure of the QIL structure. The numerical result of compressive equivalent strain indicates the critical point in 0 degree layer is near the inside surface of the open hole in the transverse axial direction. The crack initiation of the compressed fiber by micro-buckling mechanism was observed inside the surface of the open hole. After the load reached the

maximum and the failure was initiated, the catastrophic failure came quickly. The OHC of the QIL at high temperature also complies with this failure mechanism. Therefore, the master curve of SIFT parameter for the compressive equivalent strain of fibers was used to construct the predicted master curve of long term OHC strength.

Figure 9 shows the comparison between the predicted master curve of OHC strength and the experiment data. Good agreement has been achieved. As proved the validity of the time-temperature dependence of SIFT critical parameters, and the feasibility of long-term OHC strength of QIL by SIFT critical parameters.

Fig.8: Normalized failure index in QIL $[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$ of TR30S/epoxy at critical point

Fig.9: Comparison of predicted and experimental OHC strength QIL $[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$ of TR30S/epoxy

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the strain invariant failure theory (SIFT) and time-temperature superposition principle by accelerated testing method (ATM), the SIFT/ATM method was established. The time-temperature dependent SIFT critical parameter master curves can be applied to predict

the long term open hole compression (OHC) strength of CFRP laminate based on fiber and matrix resin failure mechanism in micro-level. The validity of the time-temperature dependence of SIFT critical parameters was confirmed by predicting the long term OHC strength of CFRP quasi-isotropic laminates.

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